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Vedic Agriculture and its Implementation in Modern Farming: A Review

Garima¹ & Namita Joshi²

Abstract

Agricultural practices are very old, which have been started in the *Vedic* era. Many texts such as *Surapala's Vṛkṣāyurveda*, *Kṛṣi Parashara*, *Kashyapīyakṛṣisukti*, *Kautilya's Arthashastra*, *Manusmṛiti*, *Amarakosha*, *Varāhamihira's Bṛhat Saṃhitā* describe the agricultural tools, methods, and techniques which were used in ancient time. *Vaisyavargaha* briefly explain the crop suitability according to the type of soil. Agriculture was declared one of the most respectable works in *Vedas*. Use and the benefits of *Panchgavya*, *Kunapajala*, *Beejamrit*, *Jeevamirrit*, *Compost tea*, *Matka khad*, *Vermiwash*, and *Amṛtapānī* were described in the *Vṛkṣāyurveda* and *Vedas*. Implementation of these products enhances the productivity of crops.

Keywords: Agriculture, Organic farming, Soil, Veda

Introduction

Vedas are considered an ancient treasure, which not only describes the way of living but also deals with various aspect of life and sources which helps to maintain a suitable environment for all living beings. The Vedic period was considered from c.1500-500 BCE (Sharma et al.). This was the period when Vedic Aryans started cleaning forests and adopted agriculture for their life-hood. The rise of śramaṇa movements, large states, and big cities (*mahājanapadas*) brings the Vedic period towards an end. Vedas also give an account of agriculture and its related practice as it was considered very

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crucial for the survival of human beings. In Sanskrit, the word *kṛṣi* is equivalent to agriculture and it is used many times in *R̥gveda* (Michael Brattus Jones). A detailed description of agriculture and its related aspects was found in post-Vedic literature. Going through the ancient literature it was seen that this occupation was considered the best, which not only provide wealth to farmers but also give happiness and prosperity. The composition of many Vedic scriptures including the *Samhitā* to the *Sutras* was done between c. 1500 BCE to c. 5th century BCE (Debi Prasad Chattopadhyaya and Lallanji Gopal Chapter 15: 5). Many texts like *Surapala's Vṛkṣāyurveda*, *Kṛṣi Parashara*, *Kashyapiyakṛṣisukti*, *Kautilya's Arthashastra*, *Manusmriti*, *Amarakosha*, *Varāhamihira's Bṛhat Samhitā* mention the role of agriculture practices, arboriculture, plant biodiversity, and horticulture (Gopal). The process of vegetable, cereals, and fruit cultivation along with irrigation practices and the use of cow dung manure for maintaining the fertility of soil is also mentioned briefly in these scriptures.

Land and Soil

Depending upon the soil's physical characteristics, fertility, and irrigation different lands were described in the *Amarakosha* (Jha), given in Table 1.

Table 1. Showing different land as described in Amarakosha.

S. No.	Name of different land mentioned in Sanskrit	Meaning in English
1.	<i>Urvara</i>	Fertile
2.	<i>Ushara</i>	Barren
3.	<i>Maru</i>	Desert
4.	<i>Aprahata</i>	Fallow
5.	<i>Shadvala</i>	Grassy
6.	<i>Pankikala</i>	Muddy
7.	<i>Jalaprayah</i>	Watery
8.	<i>Kachchaha</i>	Land contiguous to water

9.	<i>Sharkara</i>	Loaded with Pebbles and limestone
10.	<i>Sharkaravati</i>	Sandy
11.	<i>Nadimatruka</i>	Land watered from river
12.	<i>Devamatruka</i>	Rainfed

Vaisyavargaha mentioned the soil in relation to crop means it described the soil according to crop suitability (“Vedic Agricultural Practices”). Along with soil description, maintaining soil fertility by manuring and rotation of crops was also described in Ṛgveda. Cow dung was preferred in Vedic times as it is considered a major source of nitrogen. *Kosambi* and *Kautilya* also spoke about crop rotation, which is mentioned in *Arthashastra*. Two types of cow dung manure *i.e.* farmyard cow dung and stable (gostha), were used in the Vedic period. For nitrogen fixation use of barley husk in soil was described in *Varāhamihira* in the 6th Century AD (Ramprasad).

Origin and development of Agriculture:

The lord *Brahma* was regarded as the inventor of agriculture by *Mārkaṇḍeya purāṇa*. According to this, at the beginning Earth yields all types of vegetables and crops but with time they become unproductive after that Brahma got various types of seeds by churning soil, but shortly he realized that the crop productivity became lesser than the initial, then he originated the concept of Agriculture and bought it in practice. Since then, agriculture become a need for human survival. However, the origin of agriculture is described differently in *Viṣṇu Purāṇa* and *Bhāgavata Purāṇa*, these regarded the son of King Vena named *Prithu* as the inventor of agriculture. In *Atharvaveda*, it was mentioned that for the very first time, farming and grains were grown by King *Prithu Vainya (Raychaudhuri and Kaw)*. Agriculture has been given importance by Vedic seers because they knew that it was the only option to cope up with food scarcity. For the survival of human beings *Anna* (grain) production is important and its production occurs by agriculture so agriculture become a basic necessity for human survival. *Yajurveda* says that one should do agriculture and make some efforts to produce large quantities of grains, and the life of humans depends on agriculture *i.e.*

‘*te kṛṣiṃ ca sasyaṃ ca manuṣyā upajīvanti*’ (Atharva. 8.10.24)

To aware about the importance of agriculture Vedic seer says:

*akṣairmā dīvyah kṛṣimit kṛṣasva vitte ramasva
bahumanyamānaḥ*

*tatra gāvaḥ kitava tatra jāyā taname vi caṣṭe savitāyamaṛyaḥ
(10.Ṛgveda 10.34.13)*

This means, o gamblers, don't do gambling instead emerge in agriculture, which will give you, wealth, by which you can earn money, joy, domestic animals, and can live a happily married life.

Agriculture is regarded as human welfare in *Taittiriya Samhita* and *Yajurveda*. A person possesses the most quantity of grains respected most in society. Gods like *Pusa* and *Indra* are also considered to engage in agricultural practices. *Taittiriya Samhita* described agriculture as *Chandas*, which means it likes as music to human life, which fill the life of human with delight. *Bruhatparasara* also says that *kṛṣeranyatra no dhamo na la bhah kṛṣaṣato'nyataḥ* (11. *Bṛhatpārāśara*-5/185) which means agriculture is only the religion and there is no businesses profitable than this.

Kṣetrapati, *Go*, *Parjanya*, *Apah*, *Prithvi*, *Viśvedevāḥ*, *Aksa*, and *Araṇyāni* are various *sūkta* of *Ṛgveda* which also describe the value of agriculture for living beings. Ślokas available in *Atharvveda* depict that at that time most agriculture depends on rainwater, as mention of prayers to the god of rain available in it (*Sabhapandit*). It also describes the first process of farming which is ploughing by cattle and sowings seeds.

Kṛṣi parāśara says that one can become *bhupati* even by performing agriculture. Even the people having wealth of gold, garments, silver, and jewels also depend on farmers for food. It doesn't matter how wealthy one becomes but to diminish the hunger everyone has to depend on food. Food is life, strength, and everything. All the people, the divines, and the demons have to depend on food for survival. Food comes from grain and grain is provided by agriculture (*Parāśara*). *Mahabharata* and *Valmiki's Ramayana* also state people who engaged in agriculture live a more prosperous and happy life. *Śukra nīti* says that river water irrigated land is best suited for agriculture (*Aquique Chapter 3*).

Agriculture Essential and Management of Agriculture

Agriculture depends on various factors like farmers, type of soil, seeds, farming techniques, manure, agriculture implements,

irrigation, etc. Farmers are a fundamental part of agriculture practice. Agriculture can't be possible without farmers so they are placed at higher rank and entitled as *Kṣetrapati*, *Kṛṣaka*, *Kṛṣikā*, *Kṛṣivala* etc. In Vedas, farmers are also called as *Kinasa*.

According to *Pāṇini*, farmers are of three kinds (Kaushik):

Ahali- Farmers doesn't own ploughs

Durhali- farmers own old ploughs

Suhali- who own ploughs or good land

Atharvaveda also says that a farmer's education is very important. Farmers who were educated about *Varta Vidya* can enhance the productivity of their fields. *Bruhatparasara* says that an educated farmer has enough knowledge of various agricultural steps and never faces poverty.

Field preparation and manuring:

Farmers of the *Ṛgveda* period had knowledge of various types of soils and crops. Repeated ploughing was used to prepare the soil for cultivation. After ploughing soil was soaked with water. *Lāṅgala* and *sira* were Vedic terms for the plough. The use of horses for ploughing was also mentioned in the mantras of *Ṛgveda*. Punishment was recommended by *Manu*, the lawmaker, for the adulteration of seeds. It simply illustrates the importance of good seeds in the Vedic period. For good germination, seeds were coated with flour of sesame, black gram, and rice. Various herbs were listed in *Shurapala*, used in seed treatment. For cotton seeds treatment of cow dung was used to enhance germination rate. *Parashara* says that manure will help to produce a good yield. Manure formed by soaking sheep and goat excreta, pulverized sesame, and barley in water for seven nights was described in the *Agni Parānā*. Application of this manure helps in increasing the rate of fruiting and flowering in plant species. In the Vedic period, as a pre-sowing treatment, honey and clarified butter formed manuring is used for barley seeds (Dwivedi).

Figure. 1. Showing the ancient Vedic agricultural practices and Storage

methods

Agricultural implements

Various agricultural tools are used during the Vedic period some of them which are mentioned in *R̥gveda* given below (Roy):

S. No.	Use of Tools	Tools mentioned in Vedic Texts	Meaning in English	Main Function
1.	Forest Clearance tools	<i>Svadhiti, Paraśu</i>	Axe	Used to cut trees
2.	Soil treatment	<i>Dāṭṛ</i>	Mower	For grass cutting
3.	Soil treatment	<i>Taittiri, Samhita</i>	Roller	Making field even
4.	Tillage implements	<i>Lāṅgala</i>	Small plough	Ploughing
		<i>Sīra</i>	Heavy plough	Ploughing
5.	Harvesting tools	<i>Dāṭṛ</i>	Crook-ed knife shaped sickle	Crop Harvesting
		<i>Sṛṇī</i>	Sickle	Crop Harvesting
		<i>Jeta</i>	Reaping hook	Crop Harvesting
6.	Transporting tools	<i>Anasa</i>	Carts	
		<i>Sakata</i>	Wagon	

Irrigation

Natural irrigation and artificial irrigation, these two types of irrigation were known by Vedic people. Natural irrigation comprises rainwater and river water. In *R̥gveda*, many mantras mention the importance of rain for the production of 'anna', grains, and the increase of cattle. Small streams formed from rainwater, used for irrigation, and water was lifted by *Dronī* (like a bucket). Two main rivers viz.

Sarasvati and *Sindhu*, its seven tributaries, were used for irrigation in the Vedic period. *Sindhu* River was considered a perennial water source. *Ṛgveda* describes the use of *Sindhu* and two of its streams, flowing westerly and easterly. It was written that *Sindhu*-associated fields were rich in corn production. *Vajinivati* also describes that the *Sindhu* River water has a rich fertility capacity. It was stated in Vedas that as it moves downwards it divides into seven tributaries, and all of them enhance the fertility of fields and increase the production of 'anna'. The second river was the *Saraswati*, which arose at the valley of the Siwalik range which was the source of non-perennial water. It gets the water from the drainage of perennial rivers like *Yamuna*, *Indus*, and *Satluj* and from rainfall. It provided water from Punjab to *Saurashtra* including *Rajasthan*. It contributes to irrigation either by surface flow or by sub-soil flow.

For artificial irrigation, water was stored in the non-flowing streamlets formed due to rainwater collected with the help of *Droṇī* and used for irrigation purposes. *Ṛgveda* also described the process of lifting water filled bucket from a well with the help of a stone wheel which acts like a strap. The introduction of the use of dams and reservoirs for irrigation purposes was found in *Yajurveda*. The use of a canal system and channelizing of the river for irrigation was also described in *Atharvaveda*, *Kauśika sutra*, and *Gṛhya-sūtra* (*Prasanna and Aithal*).

Vedic *kṛṣi* implementation in modern agriculture

After the use of insecticides and fertilizers, field production rise rapidly in the 20th century. However, with time due to extensive agriculture, the use of fertilizers, and adaptation to pests, the quality of crops and food retards with time. Now most of the farmers and people started shifting towards organic farming which is devoid of chemicals in agriculture practices, and with that, Vedic *Kṛṣi* emerged once again. Vedic science-based organic farming is termed "*Chaitanya Kṛṣi*" (Gaikwad). Cow urine is considered one of the most valuable products of cows which have been used in medicine and agriculture practice since the Vedic period. Cow urine was found to be favorable in enhancing the productivity of mustard, rice, maize, etc (Choudhary et al.). Mixture of 5% cow urine + 5% cow dung and 5 % *neem* seed kernel extract was found to restrict

the toxic effect of larva and eggs of *Helicoverpa armigera* commonly known as cotton bollworm. *Vṛkṣāyurveda* and Vedas described the benefits of *Panchagavya*, *Kunapajala*, *Beejamrit*, *Jeevamirit*, Compost tea, *Matka khad*, Vermiwash and *Amṛtapānī* (RK Naresh et al.).

S. No.	Inputs	Ingredients
1.	<i>Panchagavya</i>	Cow dung, cow dung slurry, cow urine, cow milk, curd, and cow butter oil
2.	Vermiwash	Cow dung, earthworms
3.	Compost Tea	Vermicompost
4.	<i>Matla Khad</i>	Cow dung, cow urine, water, jaggary
5.	<i>Beejmirit</i>	Cow dung, cow urine, cow milk, limestone, water
6.	<i>Jeevamirit</i>	Cow dung, cow urine, jaggary, pulse flour, fertile soil, water
7.	<i>Amṛtapānī</i>	Cow butter oil, honey, cow dung, water

Among all of them, the highest nitrogen content and maximum microbial population were found in *Panchagavya*. Their results showed that Vedic *kṛṣi* and cowpathy has lesser input cost which financially gives less burden to small and marginal farmers. These techniques however give effective outputs by suppressing the growth of pathogens by producing anti-fungal, anti-bacterial compounds, siderophores, and hormones and enhance productivity. Quality and quantity of parameters and yield of *Bhindi* crop significantly increase if the seeds were treated along with *Albizia lebbek* as green manure and provided with foliage spray formed from the leaf extract of *Annona squamosal*, the same results were obtained with maize crop (V. Anbukkarasi and A. Sadasakthi). Swaminathan and Premalatha (Swaminathan and Premalatha) revealed that *Gliridica* leaf incorporation before the sowing of green gram and the use of spray foliage formed from the leaf extract *Aegle marmellos* after sowing was found most beneficial for green gram. Prior findings also revealed that the yogic method of agriculture (meditation + organic) has microbial-rich soil, and germination of seeds occurs one week earlier. The spray of biogas slurry along with *Panchagavya* also enhances the yield of Maize crop (Somasundaram et al.).

Combined use of *Panchagavya* along with inorganic fertilizer also provided the highest yield of fresh baby corn. Four times spray of 3 percent *Panchagavya* on an interval of 10 days, starting from day 15 after sowing of seeds with recommended fertilizer dose was found most suitable (Vimalendra and Wahab). Analysis of *beejamrutha* determined the presence of beneficial organisms which protect the crop from seed-borne and soil-borne pathogens. Some bacteria have the capability of phosphate solubilization, nitrogen fixation, hormones like auxin and gibberellic acid production, and suppression of *Sclerotium*, which was also found in it (Sreenivasa et al.). Different concentrations of cow urine, *jeevarmrutha*, and *Panchagavya* enhance the productivity of Capsicum crops (Boraiah et al.). Vermiwash obtained from vermicompost units is an organic drainage. It is a good source of amino acids and dissolved nutrients and acts as a potential source for plant growth (Das et al.). The use of vermiwash with various biopesticides like neem plant part and garlic bulb has n positive effects on the productivity, growth, and flowering of *Cajanus cajan* and *Cicer aritimum*. It not only induces early flowering but also reduces the infection of *Helicoverpa armigera* (bollworm).

Conclusion

Agriculture practices were briefly described in Vedic scripture. It cannot be denied that farmers of the Vedic time period used various types of agricultural management tools and techniques, which advanced as time changed. Techniques got advanced as industrialization occurred. Among them, the most crucial was manuring methods, which can be used in the replacement of fertilizers and pesticides. Use of products like *Panchgavya*, *Kunapajala*, *Beejamrit*, *Jeevamirit*, etc, can be used in organic farming. These not only benefit small-scale farmers but also help in maintaining soil health, preventing the damaging of crops, and attaining sustainable development.

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